

MODERN GADGETS AND THE INTERNET IN THE LIVES OF YOUNG PEOPLE

Nematova Diyora

Student of majoring in Pedagogy, Faculty of Pedagogy
Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

Scientific supervisor: Akhmedova Madinabonu
Makhmudjonovna

Acting associate professor at the Russian language department
Tashkent University of Applied Sciences
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728431>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23th February 2024
Accepted: 26th February 2024
Published: 28th February 2024

KEYWORDS

*modern technologies,
interactivity, media culture,
gadgets.*

ABSTRACT

this article examines the impact that modern technologies have on the younger generation and lists measures to prevent addiction to modern technologies. The features of network behavior, communication, the influence of new media on the formation of identity and Internet addiction are considered.

The modern development of society has been significantly marked by the rapid development of modern technologies. The Internet, e-mail, digital television has become thoroughly entrenched in our lives. Established media are moving into the background, especially among the younger generation. There is an element of interactivity in communication. Analyzing the influence that modern technologies have on the younger generation, we can consider the Internet as an environment that shapes social relations. Modern technologies in the lives of teenagers are both a means of communication and a source of information.

Today it is almost impossible to imagine a modern child without an electronic toy, tablet, or smartphone. It is generally accepted that children of the information age are already born with a "mouse" in their hand. Acquaintance with electronic devices begins quite early for a child, almost from birth. First, these are various convenient and functional means that allow the mother to monitor the baby from a distance (video monitors, video cameras, etc.). A little later, various toys appear that help the mother communicate with the baby at a distance, entertain and occupy the child. And then the child very quickly masters his mother's smartphone and father's tablet and organically enters into the electronic life of the family. By the age of 4-5, a modern child already confidently understands a variety of devices: from a telephone to a computer, and feels comfortable in this electronic environment, often even more confident than his older relatives.

Research on the sociocultural situation conducted in Uzbekistan reflects the intensive development of media culture, especially audiovisual (cinema, video, computer games, satellite television). Thus, all of the above greatly influences public consciousness. In modern society, the Internet, computer and smartphone give a teenager the right to individual, interactive

communication. In this mode, both the cognition of information of interest and the implementation of creative ideas can occur.

By assessing the conditions for the development of socio-economic processes in society, it is possible to identify a significant reduction in educational functions in educational institutions and families. Social networks are replacing live communication with virtual communication. Communication between children and parents fades into the background. The influence of modern technologies on the process of shaping the worldview of modern youth is increasing. The dependence of teenagers on computer games, television, and social networks is obvious. According to E.N Kurylenko, the game becomes a part of life, that is, the norm for the younger generation and replaces real life for them. From a medical point of view, computer games impair vision and cause aggression. Thus, satellite television with a multi-channel system often broadcasts programs with destructive content for the psyche.

In general, it should be noted that it is difficult to overestimate the impact of technology on children. Along with the limitless possibilities of learning about the world and the processes occurring in it, the child also encounters simpler ways of learning and development - through playful and visual perception of information about the surrounding reality. When entering school, a child becomes familiar with the culture of mass portable technologies, develops with them, and comes under both positive and negative influence of various aspects of modern technologies. It cannot be denied that over the past decades, technologies have made such an unprecedented leap up the ladder of progress that it is difficult to imagine modern life without them, therefore, they can already be considered a certain tool for the primary socialization of modern generations.

Today, the frequency of use of electronic devices around the world reaches millions of hours per day, almost every person can hardly imagine their day without a smartphone or laptop. Children also can no longer live without their electronic devices, which are perhaps even more important to them than to adults. Children are more emotional and sensitive to mobile devices. For an adult, the device itself is often unimportant - it is simply a tool for accessing the global network or a device for performing work functions and obligations; the gaming and cognitive aspects fade into the background.

Things are different for children and teenagers. A gadget for a child is not only a tool, it is also a favorite toy, like a car or a doll for previous non-information generations. At the same time, this is also a way to stand out from the crowd, or, on the contrary, an element of belonging to one's social group. When smartphones and multi-devices first became widespread, the happy owners of such devices found themselves in the center of attention of peers who wanted to see, touch a new product of computer technology, and join this culture.

Naturally, such an active entry and presence of electronic devices, especially gaming ones, in the lives of children causes the most contradictory opinions of their parents, teachers, and specialists. Quite a lot of work has been written about the influence of gaming devices on children in a variety of fields of knowledge. Experts are trying to compare and contrast the positive and negative consequences of this presence in the lives of children.

According to official statistics, today about 10% of users worldwide are considered Internet addicts. In our country, psychiatrists give a figure of 4-6%. Almost half of Europeans said they couldn't live without their mobile phone, and 42% said they couldn't live without their laptop.

About 10% of respondents admitted to having several obvious signs of psychological dependence.

According to the results of a survey of residents of six large cities of Uzbekistan by experts from the Laboratory of Social Technologies, it turned out that in Uzbekistan people are primarily "sick" of a mobile phone. Thus, 85% of young residents aged 18 to 35 said that they could not live without a cell phone. And half of the respondents are psychologically dependent on portable music devices. Other favorite gadgets include digital cameras, PDAs, and even portable DVD players and digital voice recorders.

The younger generation, which does not yet have formed spiritual and moral values, cannot always distinguish between truth and deception, illusions, and real values. Measures to prevent dependence on modern technologies include setting clear requirements for the use of gadgets and access to the Internet, and the use of monitoring programs. So, for example, there is a "Game Control" program that can distinguish the educational process from gaming activities. During the learning process, no actions take place, and when entering the game, the monitor goes dark. A teenager should develop a culture of communication with a computer, aimed at obtaining information useful for intellectual development. We can say that work to counter the influence of modern technologies on the younger generation should be carried out on a large-scale, regularly and systematically, in close cooperation, first of all with parents, then teachers and other specialists who are involved in the development of the child's abilities.

Drawing a conclusion from the above, we can say that it is not worth introducing a ban on the use of modern devices. We live in the age of technology, so knowledge in this field is necessary in the future. Most often, addiction to gadgets develops as a result of the replacement of real communication with various devices. Therefore, the main thing is parental attention and control of the time the child spends with a computer or tablet.

Thus, the formation of a new information person is impossible only through the activities of two traditional social institutions - the family and the education system, which have always been responsible for the primary socialization of the younger generations and their effective and conflict-free entry into the world of knowledge, norms and values of society. The new social reality requires the development of new mechanisms and taking into account newly emerged socio-cultural circumstances that influence the activities of these traditional institutions. However, we must remember that in solving the "man - gadget" problem, responsibility still belongs to the person.

References:

1. Salieva, Z. Z. (2018). Reading comprehension and comprehension strategies. *Учёный XXI века. Международный научный журнал*, (7-1), 42.
2. Salieva, Z. Z. (2024). DISTRACTERS OF MOTIVATION IN PRODUCING A WRITTEN TEXT OF STUDENTS IN EFL CLASSROOM. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 3(4 SPECIAL), 599-602.
3. Salieva, Z. (2023). SOME CHALLENGES FACED BY EFL STUDENTS ON WRITING SKILL. *UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH*, 1(7), 69-75.
4. Салиева, З. З. (2023). YOZISHNI ORQITISHNING XUSUSIYATLARI VA YONDASHUVLARI. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 6(3).

5. Гулрух, С. (2022). ВО 'LAJAK BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O 'QITUVCHILARINI IJODIY FAOLIYATNI TASHKIL ETISHGA TAYYORLASH PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA: Saidova Gulruh Halim qizi, Nizomiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (1), 208-214.
6. Qizi, S. G. H., & Qizi, H. H. H. (2023). TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING "4K" KOMPETENSIYALARI: KREATIVLIK, TANQIDIY FIKRLASH, KOMMUNIKATSIYA, KOOPERATSIYA. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 12), 430-432.
7. Saidova, G. (2020). CREATIVE CLASSES AS A MEANS OF FORMING PERSONAL AND COMPETENCY-BASED QUALITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PRIMARY CLASSES. In *ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ* (pp. 20-23).
8. Saidova, G. (2020). ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF THE TEACHER OF PRIMARY CLASSROOM IN THE PERIOD OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 86-90).
9. Gulchexra, K. (2023). FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(03), 40-44.
10. Кахарова, Д. С. БЎЛАЖАК ЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER Саидова Гулрух Халим қизи.
11. Ostonovich, B. O., & Khudayberdievich, S. H. (2023). Linguistic Analysis of Knowledge Issues in Psychological Discourse. *Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan*, 1(5), 355-369.
12. Bobokalonov, O. (2023). FRENCH SHIFONEMAS IN PHRASEOLOGICAL CONSTRUCTION ON HISTORICAL SOURCES. *АКТА NUUz (O'zMU Xabarlari)*.
13. Bobokalonov, O. (2023). Les phytophraséologismes ou phytophrasèmes. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 31(31).
14. Aripova, S. (2024). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 98-101.
15. Tohirovna, A. S. (2023). ENHANCING INDEPENDENT LEARNING STRATEGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH CASE STUDIES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(11), 651-652.
16. Aripova, S. T. (2023). INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA TALABALARNING IJODIY MUSTAQILLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 259-263.
17. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 7(1), 118-123.

18. Taxirovna, A. S. (2023). Lingua-cultural aspects of the translation of English and Uzbek stories. *Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany)*, 536-540.
19. Aripova, S. (2023). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS. *Science and innovation*, 2(C12), 37-42.
20. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS, SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI.
21. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2024). Objective Factors Affecting Uzbekistan's Access To The Bologna Agreement. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 29, 16-19.
22. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2024). THE INFLUENCE OF THE BOLOGNA PROCESS ON YOUTH'S WORLDVIEW. *Confrencea*, 1(1), 270-274.
23. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2023). Issues of Spiritual and Moral Education of the Mature Generation in Independent Uzbekistan. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(3S), 3864-3873.
24. Moydinova, E. (2021). THE ROLE OF MODERN ENGLISH TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGE OF DIGITALIZATION. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
25. Moydinova, E. (2022). INGLIZ TILINI O 'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
26. Moydinova, E. (2022). UNIVERSAL MASOFAVIY TA'LIM SHAROITIDA VEB-KVEST TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISHNING SAMARADORLIGI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
27. Odinaxon, I. (2023). TURLI TIZIMLI TILLARDA TARJIMON MAHORATI. *UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE*, 1(4), 27-32.
28. Ismanova, O. (2023). NEMIS VA OZBEK TILLAR KESIMIDA TARJIMONNING TARJIMADA LEKSIK SINONIMLARDAN TANLAB FOYDALANISH USLUBLARI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11 Part 2), 157-160.
29. Axrorova, R. U., Urunbayevna, I. O., & Ibrohimjon ogli, Q. A. (2022). XORIJIY TILLARNI OQITISHDA HAR BIR OQUVCHI BILAN INDIVIDUAL SHUGULLANISH VA KOPRIK TIL MOHIYATI. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(12), 22-24.
30. Kenjabaev, Ж. (2022). The implementation of literature in teaching speaking for advanced students. *Общество и инновации*, 3(2/S), 262-265.
31. Kenjabaev, J. A. (2022). METHODS THROUGH THE INTERNET IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Экономика и социум*, (12-2 (103)), 67-70.
32. Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). Communicative Language Teaching And The System Of Exercises. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 1017-1022.

- 33.** Кенжабаев, Ж. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ЭТАП РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ О ЯЗЫКЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (2 (105)), 704-707.
- 34.** Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH THROUGH INTERNET SITES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 3(11), 59-71.
- 35.** Kenjabayev, J. A. Linguistic features of the development of oral speech competence of students of the direction of physical culture education (on the example of sports terminology). *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences.-UK*, 11, 48-51.
- 36.** Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH THROUGH INTERNET SITES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 3(11), 59-71.
- 37.** Кенжабаев, Д. (2023). METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON INTERNET RESOURCES. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(11).
- 38.** Kenjabayev, J. A. (2024). Modern Teaching Methods in Teaching English. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 3(1), 52-56.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY